

Experiential Learning Model in Improving Learning Outcomes of Christian Religious Education: Papuan Case

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Abstract--- *Experiential learning is a learning process, a process of change that uses experience as learning media or Kolb's Experiential Learning model (2005). The advantage of the experiential learning model is that the results can be felt by students through experience more effectively and can achieve the objectives of learning outcomes to the fullest. Some of the benefits of experiential learning models in building and enhancing group collaboration, in case studies in Papua, include: 1) developing and increasing interdependence among group members, 2) increasing involvement in problem-solving and decision making, 3) identifying and utilizing hidden talent and leadership, 4) increasing empathy and understanding among group members. Learning experience learning models for students provide increased learning outcomes where students have high enthusiasm and confidence in learning*

Keywords--- *Experiential Learning, Learning Result, Papua*

I INTRODUCTION

Education is a conscious effort and is carried out by adults (educators) by planning, programmed and controlled to prepare individuals through teaching guidance activities or exercises for their role in the future. With that education, students (adolescents) actualize the potential they have through educational tools or media so that students (adolescents) can find their activities and can experience positive changes in aspects of their personality concerning cognitive, affective, and psychomotor changes.

The quality of education needs to be a priority for every school to improve human resources. However, most schools experience learning problems, especially those related to student learning outcomes which decline due to the influence of promiscuity, the internet, PlayStation, inattention of parents, less discipline in schools and so forth. This can be seen from the results of the Education for All Development Index (EFA) in Indonesia decreasing each year. In 2011, Indonesia was ranked 69 out of 127 countries and declined compared to 2010, which was in the 65th position. The index issued in 2011 by UNESCO was lower than Brunei Darussalam (34), and four ranks behind Malaysia (65).

The quality of education in Indonesia at this time can be said to be still very low, and this is evidenced by UNESCO data (2000) about the ranking of the Human Development Index (Human Development Index), which is the composition of the rankings of educational attainment, health, and income per capita which shows, that the index

Indonesian human development has declined. Among 174 countries in the world, Indonesia ranks 102nd (1996), 99th (1997), 105th (1998), and 109th (1999).

The quality of education in Indonesia is also inseparable from the progress of the nation and state. The progress of the nation and is seen from the development of the quality of its human resources (HR) and the extent to which the quality of human resources depends on the quality of life owned by human resources. The index of human quality in Indonesia (Human Development Index = HDI) in 2017 is around 0.694 and located ranked 116th in the world in the 'Medium HDI' group. Singapore, which has an HDI of 0.932 ranks 9th in the very high group in 2017, showing that Indonesia is still far behind the quality of its Human Resources compared to Singapore.

Based on the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) Survey, the quality of education in developing countries in the Asia Pacific, Indonesia ranks 10th out of 14 countries. As for the quality of the teachers, the quality is at level 14 of 14 developing countries.

Research from the United Nations for Development Program (UNDP) 15 September (2004) has also announced the results of studies on human quality simultaneously throughout the world through its report entitled Human Development Report (2004). In this annual report, Indonesia ranks only 111th out of 177 countries. When compared with neighbouring countries, Indonesia's position is far below that.

The results of the Third International Mathematics and Science Study-Repeat-TIMSS-R study, 1999 (IEA, 1999) showed that, among the 38 participating countries, the achievement of Indonesian junior high school class 2 students was ranked 32nd for Natural Sciences, 34th for Mathematics. In the world of higher education according to Asia Week magazine from 77 universities surveyed in the Asia Pacific, it turns out that the four best universities in Indonesia are only able to rank 61st, 68th, 73rd and 75th.

According to the World Bank Report (Greaney and Kellaghan, 1996), the IEA (International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement) study in East Asia shows that reading skills of fourth-grade elementary school students are ranked lowest. Average reading test scores for elementary students: 75.5 (Hong Kong), 74.0 (Singapore), 65.1 (Thailand), 52.6 (Philippines), and 51.7 (Indonesia).

Student learning outcomes of the experimental class are better than the control class, which has an average learning outcome of 81.79 with classical completeness of 97.43%. The level of effectiveness of the field trip learning in increasing students' concern for the environment shows a score of student awareness of 87.18% (very concerned) while the completeness of student activity classically is 89.75% with the criteria quite active, active and very active. Students gave positive responses to the application of Field Trip learning methods on environmental change and waste recycling materials with an average of 93%. (Yuliati; 2014)).

This is reinforced by the results of research (Newman & Blackorby, in Larson 2002) that most students experience learning problems that have an impact on decreased learning outcomes. The results of his research revealed that 32% of students experience learning problems, while 57% of students experience problems with emotional or psychological disorders. McGrath, (2003); argues that the main problem of student learning is (a).

learning activities and objectives, (b). learning related to the development of learning While Horn & Nunez (2000) that 38% of students consult more about counsellors about learning problems, while 16% about other program problems that exist in schools.

Furthermore, the results of the World Bank report on Education in Indonesia show that education in Indonesia needs to be addressed in student learning problems. Learning problems are inseparable from problems in the learning process because learning is a change in behaviour that is relatively sedentary and occurs as a result of practice or learning experience. Therefore teachers need to develop effective learning models that can improve student learning outcomes. One learning model that can be used by teachers is the experiential learning model. Experiential learning is an action to achieve something based on experiences that continually experience changes in order to improve the effectiveness of the learning outcomes themselves. Based on the explanation above, the writer is interested in examining the experiential learning model in improving the learning outcomes of Christian Agma Education students of SDN Inpres VIM Kotaraja Abepura Jayapura.

II MATERIALS AND METHODS

Theoretical Review

Dewey and Nagel (2008) note that there is a relationship between education and one's experience. Furthermore, (Simmons; 2006; Cranton (2012) conveys that education as a whole begins with the learning experience (Latupeirissa & Sayd, 2019). Experiential learning (EL) experts agree that experience is the core of the learning process. Beard and Wilson define EL as an active engagement process. EL has been a process in which knowledge is gained from the transformation of experience (Kolb and Kolb; 2005; 2008).

According to Hidayat (2019); there is an increase in the learning experience with learning outcomes. The results of the study said that there was an increase in learning outcomes through the application of experiential learning. It could be seen (1) the application of experiential learning saw that teacher activity increased by 15.39%, which in the first cycle was 84.6% to 100% in the second series; (2) supporting factors (a) the presentation of the problem more clearly and in detail by the teacher following the learning objectives, (b) more active student participation in learning and, (c) a pleasant, relaxed, and responsible learning arrangement in the form of discussion. (d) Overall, student learning activities increased by 16.5%, (e) cognitive aspects of learning outcomes increased by 12.56% while the affective aspects of student learning outcomes by 12.64 and psychomotor results increased by 5.92%.

This is also reinforced by the results of Primary research (2014); there is an increase in student learning outcomes and activities through experiential learning using classroom action research (CAR). Kolb and Kolb (2005; 2008); suggests three characteristics of experiential learning models, namely 1) learning is best accepted as a process, where concepts are obtained and modified from experimental activities, not stated in the form of products, 2) learning is a continuous process departing from experience, and 3) the learning process requires conflict resolution (Wita et al., 2007).

The experiential learning model emphasizes the role of experience in the learning process, the importance of active student involvement, and intelligence as an impression of the interaction between students and their environment (Yusof et al., 2014). Prior experiences are very important in learning which is a starter in the ongoing learning process. Kolb and Kolb (2005; 2008); convey "learning is a process, in which knowledge is created through the transformation of experience". Learning activities is a process. Knowledge is formed through the transformation of the student experience.

Therefore, experiential learning models are prepared and implemented by teachers of the things that are owned by students. Even this principle relates to experience in carrying out tasks and work as well as in ways of learning that are normally done by students (Firmansyah; 2015). The same thing was stated by According to Srikandi (2020); experiential learning is a teaching and learning process that activates learning to build knowledge and skills and values as well as attitudes through direct experience.

From the results of the writer's observation in the field that in general students have not been able to show Christian religious education learning outcomes (PAK) which have not been maximized because the teaching methods taught by PAK teachers are not appropriate. Therefore the need for appropriate teaching methods so that student learning outcomes improve. One of them is through the experiential learning model. The advantage of the experiential learning model is that the results can be felt by students through experience more effectively and can achieve the objectives of learning outcomes to the fullest. Some of the benefits of experiential learning models in building and enhancing group collaboration include: 1) developing and increasing feelings of interdependence among group members, 2) increasing involvement in problem-solving and decision making, 3) identifying and utilizing hidden talent and leadership, 4) increase empathy and understanding among group members. It also provides benefits and opportunities for students to decide what experiences they are focused on, what skills they want to develop, and how they can conceptualize the experience they are experiencing. Through this model, students learn not only to learn about mere material concepts, but this is also because students are directly involved in the learning process to be used as an experience. With the experiential learning model given by the teacher to students, it is expected that an increase in students' PAK learning outcomes.

Research Method

The research method used is a quantitative method using the type of classroom action research. Elliot (2019) action research is a study of social situations to improve the quality of activities contained therein. The population in this study were all the characteristics of the variables studied with the research target being students of class VIII who attended the education of students in grade V with a number of 63. Nawawi, (1998); said that if the population is below 100, then a sample of 50% and above 1000 of 15% can be used to guarantee it is better to add a little of the systematic amount. Based on this opinion, the researchers set 50% of the total number as research subjects. This number is considered to be representative enough to represent the total number of fifth-grade students of SD VIM II Kotaraja Abepura. So the number of students is 31 students at SD VIM II Kotaraja Abepura

III RESULTS

The results of this study are presented in two (2) cycles described below:

3.1 Results of the Final Cycle 1 Test Implementation

The teacher's observations on the activeness of students, it is seen that all students actively participate in all teaching and learning activities. However, some students are not concentrated because they disturbed each other. There were also some noisy when the teaching-learning process took place. Therefore, questions relating to lessons are often asked by the teacher to students in order to make sure that students kept concentrating. Furthermore, this situation shows that the teacher often lacked concentration. The teacher also explains the experiences of events that are happened.

3.2 Results of Cycle II Test Implementation

For the implementation of the second cycle of action, students are allowed to ask questions about the material obtained the previous week if they are not satisfied, the teacher explains. Then, what is their readiness to receive today's material? Each student discusses a personal assignment and then grouped/matched in a group division and then matched with other groups where the contents of the work are the same so that it is dominated by participants in the group who already understand the purpose of the work. Ten minutes is used to answer each question. Then collected and reported how many groups of correct answers were given the value of the group.

The questions are done privately in groups as follows. From the work of the second cycle at the first meeting, it was found that 21 students were able to work on the questions, while three students answered but were not yet finished so that the next meeting planned in cycle II as the second meeting on November 9, 2015, with the intention of all students completing this lesson. For students who have not been able to do the questions in the first cycle, the results of the test in the second cycle will be compared to 4 people who did not complete in the first cycle to be two students with the intention of all students who finished all the same results. The background review of the student turned out to be complete, and slow learning completeness, other fields of study were the same, so there was a follow-up. Namely, they were given enrichment and remedial as well as additional homework assignments. Indeed, these two students were unable to work on the questions, and the grades remained the same, not reaching the KKM set of 70.

From the preliminary data, cycle I and cycle II that the learning model in the teaching and learning process so far, most teachers use learning models that are not yet creatively appropriate in choosing learning models. At the same time, students are indeed active, but the results are contained in writing, whereas concrete actions are mainly discussing, responding, creativity or asking a little less. Researchers are trying to find a suitable model for use. Furthermore, when presenting material about Jesus Sacrifice and Forgiveness of sins in the learning experience model can involve students and be encouraged to be active in responding, Question and answer directed directly to students who are less active, as well as being allowed to report on their work and creativity in learning. When the

teacher presents the lesson and gives questions. Then allowed to mention what he understood about Jesus' sacrifice for humans.

Can be seen in the preliminary test data results on September 21, 2015, it appears that nine students have not been able to complete the questions thoroughly with a percentage of 45% of students not being able to answer or vice versa 11 students can do the questions quite well and declared complete, a percentage of 55% of students are able. After the presentation of the material in the first cycle, there was an increase in the absorption of learning material with the completeness of 16 students with a percentage of 80% absorbing Christian religious subject matter and being able to work on problems or increase 25%. Moreover, the second cycle is planned for November 9, 2015, can be seen again in the second cycle increased again to 21 students able to work on problems correctly or 88% of students can absorb this lesson and get a pretty good grade, while students who are not able to work on problems are only 12% or three students of 24 students.

Based on the finding, it is stated that the lesson has been ineffective without experiential learning. In other words, experiential learning model, in Papuan case, is one of the appropriate models. When lessons take place, the opportunity is given for students to be able to motivate students by playing an active role in lessons when much time the teacher gives to student participants. The success picture above shows completeness that the initial data gives a bigger picture of unfinished students, then the students whose maximum score is shown in the red and yellow diagram showing the second cycle results are increasing

4 CONCLUSION

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three students from 24 fifth grade students of SDN Inpres Vim II Kotaraja. From the research results in the field with the learning experience learning model for students provides increased learning outcomes where students have high enthusiasm and confidence in learning.

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